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Hellenic Naval Academy and the Educational Tug of War Traditional and Online Education in the Era of the Pandemic Crisis

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Abstract: The integration of new technologies in education contributes significantly to the learning process as it creates a laboratory learning environment where the learner reinforces elements of his/hers personality, such as autonomy, self-discipline, and self-will. The use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) for educational purposes is not limited, however, only to the classroom, nor has it exclusively a supplementary character. In modern times traditional education is often completely replaced by distance learning. Although in-person learning offers unique possibilities of educational reception, it is clear that there are not always perfect conditions for this to happen. Restrictions on availability in key factors, such as time, place, and expenses, but also health in some cases, prevent seamless education in its conventional option. The COVID-19 pandemic has driven the vast majority of the planet to self-isolation. People, apart from primary income, lack both general socialization and entertainment. The impact of the pandemic on education is also clear; however, education must activate the appropriate tools at its disposal in order to respond successfully to its work. This study focuses on the teaching and learning process during the period of COVID-19. Its purpose is to highlight Hellenic Naval Academy (HNA) and its educational strategies in order to increase flexibility, stay up to date, and offer an educational space with minimal restrictions. Starting with a brief presentation of HNA, this paper will focus on the curriculum and the way of transition from conventional education to its online counterpart. We will also take a closer look at e-learning and the two of its three forms— asynchronous and synchronous learning—which HNA offers in order to expand the educational framework and to successfully continue to contribute to the needs of the naval cadets and the Hellenic Navy.

Introduction

The coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) has affected the daily habits of millions of people over the last year. Thousands of people have become ill and died of the underlying causes of this disease. The rate of transmission of this virus is high and the way to prevent it is by hand hygiene, social distancing, and use of a face mask.

In addition, in order to reduce the transmission of the virus among humans, most countries have chosen to isolate themselves for a long time. This pandemic has affected the healthcare systems, the economy, and social life in all the countries. From a social point of view, personal contact among people has been lost; traveling from country to country has been limited;

and hotels, restaurants, entertainment venues and religious places of worship have shut down. Apart from these, sports venues such as gyms and swimming pools have also been closed.

The pandemic presupposes that social isolation is the only measure to prevent its transmission, but this isolation creates negative consequences such as mental fatigue, mood swings, stress, reduced physical activity, frustration, and boredom (Brooks et al., 2020). The result of the quarantine in humans is a decrease in activity, increased calorie intake, and weight gain. Reduced physical activity and increased food consumption due to more free time have led to a high energy intake. The long-term effects of these conditions can lead to metabolic and psychological disorders (Jiménez-Pavón et al., 2020).

The aim of the present paper is to initially introduce the reader to the vision, objectives, and main characteristics of the education process within the Hellenic Naval Academy (HNA), the main institution which trains the future officers of the Hellenic Navy. In Section I, we will outline the structure of the curriculum and the integration of traditional Navy education within the acquisition of a solid academic background adequate to the needs and demands of the twenty-first century Hellenic Navy. In Section II, we will discuss in detail the way the traditional education paradigm of the instructor-centered process via lecture attendance will benefit from the utilization of digital technologies, offer flexible alternative environments, and overcome challenges created by the physical distancing requirements in a constructive way. We will outline the main e-learning environments— asynchronous and synchronous learning—and the way they are integrated within the academic process in HNA. We will discuss the timeline of evolution, assessment, and degree of acceptance by both the student and teaching faculty communities. In Section III, we focus on the physical activities and education within HNA and the way the pandemic crisis has affected these activities. We will present special measures and modifications introduced in order to ensure a proper physical education, mental health, and social distancing within an extended isolation period at the heart of the pandemic crisis. Finally, we draw our main conclusions from the educational challenges dealt within the pandemic crisis in the HNA itself.

Hellenic Naval Academy

A. Vision and Aims

The Hellenic Naval Academy (HNA), established in 1845 and located at the port of Piraeus, is the institution for the academic, naval, and military education of the Hellenic Navy officers. The words of Thucydides—“Happy are the free and free are the brave”—convey the spirit of the education that is been offered, and together with the words of Sophocles—“Have courage; when you tell the truth, you will never go wrong”—aptly cultivate the culture and the improvement of knowledge within the institution.

Within the twentieth century, the Academy acquired a prominent status and recognition within the Greek State, and a large admission of students; it expanded its facilities and solidified a tradition of offering a high level of academic training in science, engineering, and humanities along with naval and military education. HNA is recognized by Greek law as a Higher Military and Academic Institution and by the European Commission as a European Higher Education Academic Institution. The faculty is selected and evaluated with the standard election and promotion procedures applied to all Greek universities and its members are committed fully to research, teaching, and related academic duties.

The Hellenic Naval Academy is committed to serving its objectives which are the continuous improvement and modernization of education processes along with advanced research in Naval Sciences and Technology. Modern higher educational processes require the international cooperation between HNA with other military and civil educational institutions in European countries and the rest of the world, in order to promote scientific research and expertise, enhance military training, improve the educational operations at all levels—undergraduate, postgraduate—and to disseminate the cultural heritage between the countries. HNA has adopted a strategy for the development of the cooperation which will be determined by high quality standards of partner institutions involving students, staff—both academic and military—as well as educational and research infrastructures. The continuous intention and will of the HNA is to play a leading role in the development of inter-university cooperation in all fields of naval science, technical engineering science, environmental science, basic sciences, and law science, as well as economics and humanities. Additionally, in the research field, HNA will be seeking possibilities for cooperation with recognized international and industrial institutions of all sizes, large as well as small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The aim focuses on the establishment of research infrastructures, which could improve the basic research capabilities of HNA and incorporate innovative applications for life improvement. The utilization of HNA’s

high level human resources and the exceptional level of infrastructure are the key elements for the achievement of the objective of inter-university cooperation.

The role of HNA in Greek state and society is well established through history and is reflected in the frequent presentation of its activities in media, public visits, and acknowledgements from collaborating institutes and social partners.

B. Undergraduate Education at the Hellenic Naval Academy

Cadets are enrolled each year at HNA following the highly competitive Pan-Hellenic University Entrance Examinations held by the Ministry of Education. The entry scores required are typically at a high success rate—within the top 5 to 10 percent—comparing to the scores required for entry to other Greek university departments. In addition, strict levels of physical and mental competence are required for acceptance in the academy. Following a 4-year education program, the graduates of HNA pursue the career of a naval officer in the Hellenic Navy. HNA is a highly preferable institution for studying and the Navy a highly sought-after career path for the young Greek generation. Successful candidates enroll in one of two course programs: I. The Deck Officers Program, illustrated in Table 1, which prepares the cadets for the deck officer career and typically enrolls around 40 new cadets each year, and II. The Engineers Program, illustrated in Table 2, which prepares the cadets for a career as a naval engineer officer and typically enrolls around 20 new cadets each year. In addition, a small number of successful students from Cyprus and a small number of students from Balkan, Middle East, and African countries are enrolled in the academy on the basis of state-to-state agreements between Greece and the above-mentioned countries.

Overall, with its curricula, HNA (www.hna.gr) aims to offer:

- Solid scientific education and training in a constantly developing technology environment;
- Analytical and synthetic skills which allow the assimilation and integration of scientific knowledge and technology on various fields for the successful tackling of all challenges that she/he will face in her/his career; and
- Strong character development, initiative, teamwork capabilities, courage, and

leadership for her/his functionality in the Greek Navy as well as the international environment.

Each program distributed in eight winter and spring academic semesters, each lasting for a 13-week period plus the final examination period. Some courses include laboratory practice, others require specific field exercises. In addition, each cadet is required to author a diploma thesis on a topic of her/his selection during her/his fourth year of study. A variety of topics requiring an in-depth investigation are offered from the faculties of the academic sectors. The depth of analysis has to meet the academic standards of an university diploma thesis and the thesis is completed with an oral presentation and examination.

In parallel to the academic program, cadets follow an intensive and coherently joined naval and military training program. The naval training program consists of lecture attendance, simulator practice, short period training trips onboard Navy vessels, and weekend sailing instruction and practice, as well as visits to naval stations. The majority of the naval training takes place during the summer semester and culminates with the participation of all cadets each summer in the summer training trip, a 45-day trip on board Navy vessels sailing on a scheduled trip, in the Mediterranean Sea or oceans beyond. These trips gradually develop the cadets naval skills and help them integrate successfully into the long tradition and practices of the Hellenic Navy. It must be noted that onboard naval training is an integral part of the curriculum that is a valuable complement to the cadets' classroom and laboratory education. During their life in the academy, the cadets also follow an extensive and suitably optimized athletic training program, with each one strongly encouraged to participate in a sports and athletics team, develop her/his special abilities, practice extensively, and excel in her/his favorite sport.

Table 1. Deck Officers Program, based on 2018-2019 syllabus.

1st Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
General Shipping – Coastal Navigation	3	International Regulations for Preventing/Avoiding Collisions at Sea/Ship Handling	2

Naval Skills	3	Applied Shipping/Navigation	4
Introduction to Computers	2	Computer Programming	2
Single Variable Calculus	3	Vector Analysis	3
Linear Algebra	2	Analytic Geometry – Geometry of Curves and Surfaces	3
General and Applied Physics (A)	2	General and Applied Physics (B)	2
History of the oared and sailing navies	4	Economics of Defense	2
Philosophy	2	Social Psychology	2
Foreign Languages (English, French, German) I	3	Foreign Languages (English, French, German) II	3
Total hours	24	Total hours	23
2nd Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Astronomical Navigation - Tides	4	Marine Meteorology	4
Theoretical Navigation and Applications	4	Theoretical and Applied Electromagnetism II	2
Theoretical and Applied Electromagnetism I	2	Introduction to Marine Engineering	5
Introduction to Electric Circuits Theory	3	Electrical Circuits Theory and Applications	4
Differential Equations	3	Systems Analysis and Introduction to Control Systems	3
Probability	2	Numerical Analysis	2
Theoretical Mechanics I	2	Statistics	2

Foreign Languages (English, French, German) III	3	Theoretical Mechanics II	2
Ballistics – Explosives – Antisubmarine Weapons	2	Modern Naval History	3
Total hours	25	Total hours	27
3rd Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Electronic Navigation Systems	3	Hydrography - Oceanography	3
Electronic Charts and Geographical Information Systems in Navigation and in Naval Operations	4	Naval Operations	3
Electronics I	5	Naval Artillery/Gunnery	3
Introduction to Naval Materials Science and Technology	2	Theory and Applications of Naval Military Radar and Electro optical systems	5
Introduction to Applied Mechanics	3	Electronics II	5
Introduction to Electric Power Systems	3	Experimental Strength and Failure Analysis of Materials	3
Quantum Physics and Applications	3	Mathematical Modeling and Applications	2
Operational Research – Linear Programming	2	Foreign Languages (English, French, German) V & Foreign Language IMO	3
Foreign Languages (English, French, German) IV & Foreign	2		

Language IMO			
Total hours	27	Total hours	27
4th Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Special Topics in Navigation and Ocean Sciences I	2	Special Topics in Navigation and Ocean Sciences II	2
Marine Environment and Naval Operations	3	Electronic Warfare/Underwater Acoustics	3
Tactical Systems/ C4I Networks	4	Combat Systems Engineering / Guided Missiles / PWO	4
Naval Telecommunications/Satellite and Space Systems	3	Communication Systems II	5
Communication Systems I	5	Information Security – Cryptography – Computational Intelligence	2
Leadership	2	Naval Architecture	3
Computer Networks – Internet Programming	3	Maritime Law	3
Optimization – Non-Linear Programming	2	Game Theory and Decision Making	2
Total hours	24	Total hours	24

Table 2. Engineer Officers Program, based on 2018-2019 syllabus.

1st Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours

Elements of Navigation/Shipping and Naval Skills	5	Mechanical Drawing	3
Introduction to Computers	2	Computer Programming	2
Single Variable Calculus	3	Vector Analysis	3
Linear Algebra	2	Analytic Geometry – Geometry of Curves and Surfaces	3
General and Applied Physics (A)	2	General and Applied Physics (B)	2
Chemistry	2	Economics of Defense	2
History of the oared and sailing navies	4	Social Psychology	2
Foreign Languages (English, French, German) I	3	Leadership	2
		Foreign Languages (English, French, German) II	3
		Philosophy	2
Total hours	23	Total hours	24
2nd Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Thermodynamics	3	Applied Thermodynamics	5
Fluid Mechanics	3	Auxiliary Systems and Ship Networks	3
Fuels and Lubricants Technology	3	Electric Circuits Theory and Applications	4
Theoretical and Applied Electromagnetism	4	Systems Analysis and Introduction to Control Systems	3

Introduction to Electric Circuits Theory	3	Theoretical Mechanics - Statics	4
Differential Equations	3	Numerical Analysis	2
Probability	2	Statistics	2
Foreign Languages (English, French, German) III	3	Modern Naval History	3
Total hours	24	Total hours	26
3rd Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Electronics I	5	Electronics II	5
Heat Transfer	3	Marine Reciprocating Engines	5
Marine Gas Turbines	5	Materials Science and Engineering	3
Applied Mechanics I	2	Applied Mechanics II	3
Introduction to Electric Machines	3	Electrical Power Systems	3
Theoretical Mechanics - Dynamics	4	Mathematical Modeling and Applications	2
Quantum Physics – IR Applications and Laser	2	Topics on Applications of Modern Physics	2
Operational Research – Linear Programming	2	Foreign Languages (English, French, German) V& Foreign Language IMO	3
Foreign Languages (English, French, German) IV & Foreign Language IMO	2		

Total hours	28	Total hours	26
4th Year			
Semester A	Hours	Semester B	Hours
Communication Systems I	5	Communications Systems II	5
Naval Architecture A	5	Naval Architecture B	5
Machine Elements I	3	Machine Elements II	3
Introduction to Finite Element Method	3	Applied Mechanics III	2
Naval Materials Technology	3	Experimental Strength and Failure of Materials	4
Computer Networks – Internet Programming	3	Information Security – Cryptography – Computational Intelligence	2
Optimization – Non-Linear Programming	2	Maritime Law	3
		Game Theory and Decision Making	2
Total hours	24	Total hours	26

C. Faculty and Quality Assurance

The faculty of HNA consists of around thirty members distributed among the seven academic sectors listed in Tables 1 and 2. In addition, a number of Hellenic Navy officers who fulfill the necessary academic requirements are assigned to teach the specialized courses and a number of civilian staff on various academic and athletic courses supplement each year's teaching personnel according to arising needs. Research is actively pursued by all faculty members on their academic specialty via participation in research grants, publications, and presentations on relevant international and domestic conferences and workshops.

As a higher education institute in Greece, HNA is committed to maintaining an Internal System of Quality Assurance, annually evaluating all levels and procedures of its educational, research, organizational and administrative operations. In 2021, HNA received from the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education—which is the Hellenic State Organization responsible for the continuous external evaluation of all Greek universities—the Certificate of Compliance of its Internal System of Quality Assurance. The organization chart of HNA Quality Assurance Unit (QAU) is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. HNA Quality Assurance Unit Organization Chart

The HNA has established in the last ten years the evaluation of the teaching staff and the courses taught by the naval cadets through the completion of appropriate questionnaires. The academic staff utilizes the findings from the evaluation to improve the teaching and educational process of the program courses. Additionally, these evaluations considered for the promotion of the faculty teaching staff. The rating for all questions ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest score and 5 is the highest score.

Grouping the answers of the tests in low score (which includes the answers with grade 1

or 2) and in high score (which includes the answers with grade 4 or 5) on a percentage basis, it is found for the questions concerning teachers' performance the high score is 60 percent, while the percentage of the low score is 23 percent.

The questionnaires about the quality of academic education, focusing on the clarity and the organization in the curriculum, showing that the high score (grade 4 or 5) has a percentage of 60 percent while the low score (grade 1 or 2) receives percentage of 20 percent.

The time schedule is kept to a high degree. This emerges both from the data kept in the secretariat of the department and from the point of view of the naval cadets, as it was expressed in the question "Was he consistent in his / her obligations (attendance at classes, timely correction of assignments, availability)," where the high score (4 and 5) occupied a response rate of 57 percent and low score (1 and 2) 23 percent. It is noted that the annual planning becomes known to all members of the educational community at the beginning of the academic year.

Sixty-one percent of the cadets judge from quite as great (grades 4 and 5) the consistency of the lecturers into their obligations (presence, timely correction written, and volume), and 21 percent gives a low rating to the specific question.

Also, all questions relating to the organization and implementation of clock curriculum received high scores (4 and 5) ranging between 50 and 75 percent with the exception of the question of the time spent by the naval cadet weekly in the study of each course, where the low grade receives a percentage of 69 percent, corresponding to a time of less than 4 hours.

To the question, "Am I facilitated in the systematic attendance of the courses (due to other obligations)?," responses with high scores (grade 4 or 5) for the year 2018-2019 were 59 percent of the total, while the response to low rating (grade 1 or 2) received rate of 20 percent. The results remain unchanged during the pandemic of COVID-19.

In the evaluation of the laboratories and simulators used in HNA, the high score receives the highest percentage in all questions of this section (it ranges around 52 percent), with the low score being limited to percentages of 22 percent. Therefore, the infrastructure and the quality of the laboratory exercises/spaces are considered satisfactory, and, in fact, the students' point of view is improving compared to the past.

On the contrary, in the question regarding the availability of bibliography in the library,

the high score being limited to 44 percent and the low amounting to 33 percent. This shows that the services of the library must be modernized.

I. Online Education and Hellenic Naval Academy

The above outlined traditional education of the naval cadet has as its aim, except for the classic academic background; to develop capabilities on strategy, teamwork, and networking; and to envisage values such as loyalty, effort, and effectiveness. Traditional education and physical presence are tied together. The restricted measures, which have been implemented to delay the virus expansion within the community, instantly forced the transition from traditional education to online distance education. The pandemic forced the HNA to prove its adaptability of implementing new high quality education techniques. The teaching materials used (textbooks, notes, and laboratory guides) remain the same in both pathways.

During the period of the COVID-19 pandemic the education at the HNA takes place in the form of e-learning by distance. More specifically, courses are carried out by the method of distance education, literally following the timetable during traditional teaching—supported, however, by the platforms of both synchronous education (Big Blue Button, MS Teams) and asynchronous education (Open e-Class). The implementation of synchronous and asynchronous learning plays a significant role and the fact that all parameters are considered can successfully contribute to the needs of the naval cadets and the Hellenic Navy.

Figure 2 illustrates the increment of the synchronous learning activities. In less than a month period since the beginning of isolation, the synchronous methods cover 93.75 percent of the educational effort. It is visible proof that employing effective response strategies and implementing execution plans can help recover quickly during disruptions and resume stronger than before.

Figure 3 presents the attempt to contact laboratory experiments in real-time using institutional licensed MS Teams videoconferencing software. As a result of the limitation on the in-person naval cadet education, online learning was rapidly adapted. However, as can be easily understood the absence of the lecturer-educator at the beginning of the distance learning period results in forcing a number of the cadets to lose focus. In order to mitigate this abnormal

situation while maintaining the effectiveness of the education process, small group workshops were organized between the educator and the cadets.

Figure 2. The synchronous and asynchronous teaching at the beginning of the pandemic

Figure 3. Laboratory exercise during synchronous teaching

II. Physical activity during the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) period in the Hellenic Naval Academy

It is generally known that regular exercise as a physical activity and an active lifestyle activate and strengthen the human immune system (Khoramipour et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2020) and help control body weight and mental health. Therefore, physical exercises for all people play an important protective role during this particular period of the pandemic.

To date, it is accepted that indoor sports facilities, in particular, increase the transmission of the coronavirus and the only way out is open sports facilities. In other words, playing sports in the open air is allowed without any risk, provided that relative distance between the athletes is kept, especially with activities such as running, swimming in the open sea and tennis.

These general rules have influenced the daily life of all military schools, including that of the daily sporting activities of the naval cadets. At HNA, we have tried to control extra food intake in order to avoid obesity and have created exercise programs adapted to the requirements

of the pandemic. The pandemic shows that it affects the readiness of military students while its duration cannot be predicted. Living together in military schools, that is, in a closed environment, seems to be the ideal way for the transmission of an infection. Also, viruses can be easily transmitted in the environment of ships while on educational trips. During the lockdown of the naval cadets, their youth and responsible attitude proved to be an added advantage.

The special rules of coexistence in military schools and the observance of rules played an important role in the cooperation of the athletics faculty with the cadets in order to achieve the continuity of the cadets' sporting activities. In addition, the fact that HNA quickly adapted to the pandemic requirements had a positive effect and the morning academic classes continued without being greatly affected.

Therefore, the challenge was to maintain the readiness of the naval cadets as future officers and, regarding sports, to maintain their level of physical condition as much as possible. In other words, we had to choose between partial fitness and readiness or no readiness at all. We also had to set an example to our students and future officers that in addition to theory, crisis management can be put into practice with logic and cooperation.

For the preparation of the athletic programs the following decalogue was taken into account:

1. Decreased physical activity causes a decrease in the immune and cardiorespiratory system (Susuki, 2019) while moderate-intensity systemic exercise can boost the immune system (Goh et al., 2019, Metsios et al., 2020) and is associated with a reduced incidence, duration, and severity of upper respiratory tract infections (Nieman & Wentz, 2019).
2. Distances among the athletes during the workouts were observed by managing the volume of the athletes in two different arrival hours.
3. We redesigned the sports training programs in order to maintain physical fitness and not to necessarily improve it.
4. The participation of the cadets during sporting activities and the implementation of the training programs had to be pleasant and to contain a variety in order to provide mental rest from the academic program but also from the isolation-quarantine.

5. We chose systematic moderate intensity exercise programs outdoors.
6. The exercise programs were limited in duration to about one hour and contained moderate-intensity aerobic running, strength exercises with body weight, with dumbbells or rubber bands, but also a combination of aerobic exercise and strength without exhaustion.
7. We banned team sports that included physical contact, such as volleyball and basketball, while indoor swimming was restricted to once a week.
8. Discrete supervision and the use of a face mask by the coaches were chosen without any personal contact so as to avoid any infection since daily presence at HNA was required and it would not be possible to control completely their contacts.
9. The weekly training program was sent by mail so that each sports team was informed about the exact content of the training.
10. The frequency of sporting activities was limited for each cadet to four times a week since they were not allowed to leave the HNA for long periods of time.

More specifically, the frequency of sporting activities was reduced by 20 percent from 20 times to 16 times per month. Until February 2020 (pre COVID-19) each cadet trained five times a week for 90 minutes, which included three times sporting activities and twice indoor swimming. Since March 2020 training has been reduced to four times per week for 60 minutes, one of which was swimming. Furthermore, from September 2020 to January 2021, the same training program was maintained by limiting the training sessions to 50 minutes.

The training programs over the COVID-19 period include outdoor activities such as running and muscle strengthening exercises with body weight. Finally, during swimming the number of cadets was limited to two to three cadets in each lane while there was strict supervision by a professional trainer who made sure that the protection measures were kept.

Figure 4. Training minutes per month at the beginning of the pandemic and at the start of the second wave

III. Conclusions

The pandemic crisis was—and still is—an event of unprecedented challenge to the world, societies, and every aspect of professional and social activities. Education and training at HNA faced these challenges efficiently based on the information and communication technologies which were present or became readily available. The swift transition from the traditional educational process via in person lecturing, lab exercising, etc., to the e-learning based approach allowed the uninterrupted continuation of the academic activities at HNA in the midst of social distancing enforcement. The evaluation of the naval cadets showed that the school managed to return to the level it was at the evaluation at the end of the academic year 2019. Of course, the provision of certain services must be improved, such as the bibliographic support of the homework and the diploma thesis, but also the evolution of the laboratory exercises with the

rotating physical presence of the naval cadets.

The improvisation of a modified physical training and athletics everyday program helped the naval cadets to maintain their mental health, spirits, and positive behavior during a long period of isolation within the academy premises.

The implementation of the physical training program assisted the participation of the cadets in the academic courses. From the sports evaluation tests in January 2020 and in January 2021, a non-statistically significant reduction (-1.3 percent) in the athletic ability and the general physical condition of the naval cadets was noticed.

In an era of increasingly virtual education delivery, the evaluation of how the new learning approaches could potentially affect or substantially transform the pedagogy of its cadets must be the primary obligation of every Navy organization. Blended educational programs are giving the best available outcome as evidenced from this pandemic period.

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Dr. Antonios Vantarakis was born in Patras, Greece; specialized Laboratory and Teaching Staff of Physical Education and Field Training in Hellenic Naval Academy (1999-present). He holds a Ph.D. in sports sciences from the Democritus University of Thrace, Department of Physical Education and Sports Sciences (2019); an MSc in physical education, "Maximize Athletic Performance," from the Democritus University of Thrace Department of Physical Education and Sports Sciences (2007), and BSc in physical education and sports sciences in track and field from National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Department of Physical Education and Sports Sciences, (1990). He is author or coauthor of one monograph, seven scientific articles on peer-reviewed journals, two book chapters, and seventeen announcements on peer-reviewed scientific conferences.

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